

Additional methods and results of “Cyclic seasonal variation of pollen specific IgE to six taxa over seven years: a population study”

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Abbreviations

MPS: Main Pollen Season

sIgE: Specific Immunoglobulin E

Methods

Pollen counts

The study took place in Valencia (39° 28' 50" N, 0° 21' 59" W), a city located on the east coast of Spain, in the thermo-Mediterranean climatic belt, with a long dry period of four to five months. The area has an average annual temperature of 18.3 °C and 475 mm of annual total precipitation. Pollen counts were recorded from 2012 to 2019 by one of the authors (JS), with >20-years' experience. Pollen sampling was carried out using the most widely used method worldwide, a seven-day recording volumetric Hirst Burkard type spore trap, located on the roof of a building, 20 meters above ground level. The sampler operates continuously with a suction flow rate of 10 L/min to simulate human breathing and has a drum which rotates at 2 mm/h over a Melinex tape coated with a silicone-based adhesive where the pollen particles adhere. The samples were mounted on glass slides with glycerogelatine-basic fuchsine. The methods of identifying and counting the pollen grains were performed using an optical microscope at 400 x magnification, following a standardised procedure outlined in the Management and Quality Manual. The data used correspond to daily values expressed as the number of pollen grains per cubic meter of air. The pollen grains identified were those of Platanaceae, Oleaceae, Poaceae, Cupressaceae, Urticaceae and Amaranthaceae.

Definition of study periods

The onset of the Main Pollen Season (MPS) for each species varies from year to year. To relate sIgE levels to actual pollen counts rather than historical pollen calendars, and to harmonise for the different taxa in this study, we defined pollen years, months and trimesters. To define the onset of each MPS for each taxon we used the day when the pollen count

reached 2.5% of the total count of each year, since January 1st for Platanaceae, Oleaceae, Poaceae and Amaranthaceae, and since September 1st for Cupressaceae and Urticaceae. A “pollen year” was defined as the period beginning on the day each MPS began and ending on the day the following year’s MPS begins (e.g., if the Amaranthaceae pollen year began on April 15th 2012 and the next one on March 9th 2013, the 2012 pollen year would end on March 8th 2013). The first “pollen month” began on the first day of the pollen year, the next pollen month began on the same day of the following month (e.g., if the MPS started on April 15th, the first pollen month ended on May 14th, the second pollen month lasted from May 15th until June 14th, and so on, until the end of that pollen year). Because each pollen year can start earlier or later than the previous one, the last pollen month could have more or less than 30 days, or even none at all (e.g., if the pollen year started on April 15th and the next on March 9th, the 12th pollen month would not exist). “Pollen trimesters” were defined as 1st to 4th comprising every three pollen months of each year. We assessed the years 2012 to 2018 for Oleaceae, Platanaceae, Poaceae, and Amaranthaceae. Because Cupressaceae and Urticaceae begin their MPS in Autumn, we assessed years 2013 to 2019 that began in 2012 to 2018.

Specific IgE

We retrospectively collected data from our laboratory database on sIgE levels from all samples analysed during the pollen years assessed. Samples had been obtained from children and adolescents, aged less than 18 years, seen because of rhinoconjunctivitis and/or asthma, who had had positive skin tests to pollen and in whom sIgE measurement had been indicated by the treating physician. Patients were seen for the first time by previous appointment, according to a waiting list and independently of current symptoms; likewise, the blood sample could be drawn at any date, also independently from symptoms. We measured sIgE to whole

extracts for *Platanus acerifolia* (Platanaceae), *Cupressus arizonica* (Cupressaceae), *Parietaria judaica* (Urticaceae), and *Salsola kali* (Amaranthaceae), and to molecular allergens Ole e 1 for Oleaceae, and Phl p 1+5 for Poaceae. sIgE was determined using the UniCAP System (Thermo Fisher Scientific US), and expressed as kUA/L (values >100 kUA/L were converted to 101). IgE results were grouped according to the pollen years, months and trimesters in which the samples had been obtained.

Statistical study

Data on pollen counts and sIgE levels are shown as absolute numbers and means. For comparisons and correlations, due to their non-normal distribution, we used the Kruskal-Wallis test and Spearman's coefficient. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant. SPSS 15.0 software (SPSS IBM, Chicago Ill) was used.

Authorisation

Anonymity of patients was warranted. As this was a population study, informed consent from the patients was not deemed necessary, as considered and approved by our local Ethics Committee (No. 2020-527-1).

Results

The start dates and duration of each pollen year are shown in Table S-1. The smallest variation in duration was found in Platanaceae, with a maximum of 20 days difference between the longest and shortest pollen years; the largest difference was 82 days for Cupressaceae. The differences between the earliest and latest date of start of the pollen year ranged from 18 days for Platanaceae to 54 for Cupressaceae.

Table S-2 shows the absolute pollen grain counts, the number of serum samples and the mean sIgE levels for each taxon and year. The largest difference between annual pollen counts was found for Poaceae; the load in 2013 was almost 2.5 times that in 2017; the lowest difference was 1.6 times for Urticaceae in 2013 compared to 2018. There was no significant correlation between pollen counts of the different taxa (Table S-3), partly due to the low number (seven) of observations, even though some Rho correlation values were higher than 0.4.

Table S-2 also shows the ratio between the pollen counts of the years with the highest and lowest values, which was more than double for Oleaceae, Cupressaceae and Poaceae. The highest/lowest sIgE ratio was more than double for all taxa except Oleaceae and Poaceae.

The very high and significant difference ratio for *Cupressus arizonica* is somehow artefactual and could be attributed to extreme values far from the mean. Although the difference for Oleaceae was not so high, it was statistically significant due to the higher number of samples. The results in the Figures S-1 to S-6 show the means of the seven years for quarterly and monthly results.

Platanaceae (Figure S-1).

Airborne pollen of Platanaceae was concentrated almost exclusively in one month. The highest sIgE values for *Platanus acerifolia* were found in the second to fourth months, and declined 4-6 months after the end of the season. There were significant differences between months and between trimesters. The highest/lowest sIgE ratio between months was 7.4, and that between trimesters was 3.9. Month number six showed a sIgE value out of expected, due to the low number of samples analysed, as it corresponded to August, month with limited activity in our laboratory.

Oleaceae (Figure S-2)

Pollen load of Oleaceae was concentrated in the first trimester of the pollen year, practically in two months. The highest level of Ole e 1 sIgE was found in the second to fifth months, and decreased 4-6 months after the end of the season. There was a significant difference in trimesters 1 and 2 compared to 3 and 4, and among the 12 months of the pollen year. The highest ratio of sIgE between months was 2.8, and 2 between trimesters.

Poaceae (Figure S-3).

For grasses, airborne Poaceae pollen appeared gradually, with increasing loads in the second and third months and declining from the fourth month onwards, with two-thirds of the pollen being found in the first trimester. Levels of sIgE to Phl p 1+5 peaked in the second trimester. The highest value was found in month four and next in month seven (coinciding with the second peak of grass pollen in autumn); the lowest in six to nine months after the end of the season. The ratio between the highest and lowest sIgE values was 3 between months and 2.2 between trimesters.

Cupressaceae (Figure S-4).

Cupressaceae pollen release lasted for 6–7 months, with highest loads in months 4–6. The highest sIgE values for *Cupressus arizonica* were found in months 5 to 8 (month 10, corresponding to August, again showed a value out of expected); the lowest values appeared 6-9 months after the end of the season, overlapping with the slow start of the new season. The ratio of highest to lowest sIgE values was 2.8 for months and 2 for trimesters.

Urticaceae (Figure S-5).

Pollen counts of Urticaceae were measurable practically 10 months of the year, with highest loads in month 6 to 8, and equal amounts in trimesters 2 and 3. The highest value of *Parietaria judaica* sIgE was found in months 6 to 9, and the lowest in months 1 to 3, when there were still relatively low amounts of pollen from the new season and approximately 4-5 months after the end of the previous one. The ratio of the highest to lowest values was 4.1 between months and 3.2 between trimesters.

Amaranthaceae (Figure S-6).

The pattern of results for Amaranthaceae was different. Pollen shedding lasted for six months, most of it in the second trimester, but sIgE levels for *Salsola kali* gradually decreased from the first to the fourth trimester. The ratio of the highest to lowest sIgE was 8.1 for months and 5 for trimesters.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

AM: conceptualization, methodology, data collection and analysis, writing –original. DTJ: methodology, data collection and analysis, review. SU: methodology, data collection, review. JS: methodology, data collection, review.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Datasets are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Table S-1. Dates of start and duration (days) of each pollen year. Maximal differences between the earliest and latest start, and between longest and shortest pollen years. Pollen years of Cupressaceae and Urticaceae start in autumn of the previous year (e.g. pollen year 2013 started on November 2012, etc.).

	Platanaceae		Oleaceae		Poaceae		Cupressaceae		Urticaceae		Amaranthaceae	
2012	23 mar	354	3 may	350	4 apr	338					15 apr	328
2013	12 mar	360	18 apr	363	8 mar	387	24 nov	311	29 nov	337	9 mar	388
2014	7 mar	374	16 apr	377	30 mar	363	1 oct	393	1 nov	367	1 apr	375
2015	16 mar	355	28 apr	354	28 mar	345	29 oct	361	3 nov	369	11 apr	351
2016	5 mar	369	16 apr	363	7 mar	356	25 oct	376	7 nov	366	27 mar	363
2017	9 mar	369	14 apr	388	26 feb	400	4 nov	335	7 nov	355	25 mar	388
2018	13 mar	360	7 may	344	2 apr	331	5 oct	382	28 oct	387	17 apr	353
2019							22 oct	346	19 nov	356		
Max. diff (days)	18	20	23	44	37	69	54	82	32	50	39	60

Table S-2. Total pollen count (PC), number of serum samples (N) and mean levels of specific IgE for each pollen year, means of the six pollen years, and ratio between the highest and the lowest values of pollen counts and of sIgE (highest and lowest values in bold letter).

	Platanaceae			Oleaceae			Poaceae			Cupressaceae			Urticaceae			Amaranthaceae		
		<i>Platanus acerifolia</i> sIgE			Ole e 1 sIgE			Phl p 1+5 sIgE			<i>Cupressus arizonica</i> sIgE			<i>Parietaria judaica</i> sIgE			<i>Salsola kali</i> sIgE	
	PC	N	Mean	PC	N	Mean	PC	N	Mean	PC	N	Mean	PC	N	Mean	PC	N	Mean
2012	8109	50	4.53	2381	260	13.41	860	173	12.39							545	34	8.43
2013	14064	57	3.67	2379	341	11.93	1699	220	15.99	7704	40	2.89	2145	52	7.92	497	16	4.88
2014	12516	82	7.85	2793	421	9.44	1063	216	15.78	9976	96	11.52	1451	40	7.80	687	34	6.92
2015	11650	93	3.45	3957	551	17.72	1038	282	19.65	6617	165	7.90	1380	85	9.67	640	72	5.78
2016	14848	103	7.80	2881	531	13.59	1031	273	14.84	4952	134	9.38	1357	92	10.01	511	64	5.48
2017	12815	95	6.77	3053	695	13.79	689	321	18.32	8321	158	7.71	1510	62	10.00	610	137	4.94
2018	9003	99	5.09	1713	532	10.75	740	248	13.79	7200	161	5.79	1333	59	10.03	354	101	2.56
2019										11751	250	8.05	1692	44	19.91			
Total		579			3331			1733			1004			434			458	
Mean	11858	83	5.79	2737	476	13.15	1017	248	16.14	8074	143	7.91	1553	62	10.49	549	65	5.03
p value (K-W)			0.958			0.005			0.273			.003			0.151			0.564
Ratio max/min	1.83		2.28	2.31		1.88	2.47		1.59	2.37		3.99	1.61		2.55	1.94		3.29

K-W: Kruskal-Wallis H test. N: Number of serum samples. PC: Total pollen count in grains/m³ of air. sIgE: Specific Immunoglobulin E (kUA/L)

Table S-3. Spearman's correlation between the yearly pollen counts of the different taxa (p: not significant in all cases).

		Platanaceae	Oleaceae	Poaceae	Cupressaceae	Urticaceae
Oleaceae		-0.357				
Cupressaceae		-0.143	-0.257			
Poaceae		0.321	-0.321	0.143		
Urticaceae		0.429	-0.143	0.429	0.643	
Amaranthaceae		-0.071	0.571	0.179	0.371	0.257

Figure S-1. The graph shows means and error bars of seven years pollen counts (grains/mm³ of air) for Platanaceae (upper graphics) and levels of specific IgE (kUA/L) to *Platanus acerifolia* (lower graphics), according to months (left) and trimesters (right) of “pollen year”. MPS: Main Pollen Season. N: number of serum samples in each period. The “pollen months” do not exactly match calendar months, and they vary across the years. Calendar months are shown based on the mean date of start of the MPS (March 12th).

Figure S-2. The graph shows means and error bars of seven years pollen counts (grains/mm³ of air) for Oleaceae (upper graphics) and levels of specific IgE (kUA/L) to Ole e 1 (lower graphics), according to months (left) and trimesters (right) of “pollen year”. MPS: Main Pollen Season. N: number of serum samples in each period. The “pollen months” do not exactly match calendar months, and they vary across the years. Calendar months are shown based on the mean date of start of the MPS (April 23rd).

Figure S-3. The graph shows means and error bars of seven years pollen counts (grains/mm³ of air) for Poaceae (upper graphics) and levels of specific IgE (kUA/L) to Phl p 1+5 (lower graphics), according to months (left) and trimesters (right) of “pollen year”. MPS: Main Pollen Season. N: number of serum samples in each period. The “pollen months” do not exactly match calendar months, and they vary across the years. Calendar months are shown based on the mean date of start of the MPS (March 20th).

Figure S-4. The graph shows means and error bars of seven years pollen counts (grains/mm³ of air) for Cupressaceae (upper graphics) and levels of specific IgE (kUA/L) to *Cupressus arizonica* (lower graphics), according to months (left) and trimesters (right) of “pollen year”. MPS: Main Pollen Season. N: number of serum samples in each period. The “pollen months” do not exactly match calendar months, and they vary across the years. Calendar months are shown based on the mean date of start of the MPS (October 25th).

Figure S-5. The graph shows means and error bars of seven years pollen counts (grains/mm³ of air) for Urticaceae (upper graphics) and levels of specific IgE (kUA/L) to *Parietaria judaica* (lower graphics), according to months (left) and trimesters (right) of “pollen year”. MPS: Main Pollen Season. N: number of serum samples in each period. The “pollen months” do not exactly match calendar months, and they vary across the years. Calendar months are shown based on the mean date of start of the MPS (November 9th).

Figure S-6 The graph shows means and error bars of seven years pollen counts (grains/mm³ of air) for Amaranthaceae (upper graphics) and levels of specific IgE (kUA/L) to *Salsola kali* (lower graphics), according to months (left) and trimesters (right) of “pollen year”. MPS: Main Pollen Season. N: number of serum samples in each period. The “pollen months” do not exactly match calendar months, and they vary across the years. Calendar months are shown based on the mean date of start of the MPS (April 2nd).

